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During the first half of the XIX century, internal wars and conflicts, among the Khanates deteriorated economic, social and political status in this area. This came in handy for Russian Imperia because there was a good opportunity to accomplish their previous plans.

Coming to the mid of 19ths, new colonization policy became more common among against giant countries in the world. In this competition, Russian Imperia was not an exception. As well as this, activities of Russia and England in Turkmenistan came across in the mid of 19ths Politicians of Russian Imperia were afraid that Great Britain might colonize Eastern part of Turkmenistan and Kaspiy River. There were many reasons for this. Example, England was carrying out trade and diplomatic relations with Uzbek Khanates through its colonized areas like India and Afghanistan. However, their main purpose was to not to allow Russia to complete its plans in this area and combine three Khanates against Russia so that it can itself gain the central Asian market. It is important to mention some reasons for Russia to speed up colonizing Central Asia:

1. Availability of base of the cheap raw materials to provide Russia's light Industry in Central Asia.

2. Due to Crimea War (1853-1856), loose of port areas in Black sea and to fulfill it by taking over Central Asia. By this way, moving towards the Southern sea that are resistant to icing, eliminating Russia's influence on Iran, Afghanistan, China and India so that they were able to establish trade and diplomatic relations. In this way, Turkistan was plantar for these aggressions.

3. Because Russia could not compete in European market, they wanted to take Central Asia market in order to sell their products.

4. Bringing Russian population who became very poor because of the new land reformation and providing them with land.

Because of above-mentioned economic and political reasons were regarded as their daily mission, Russian Imperia started its initial military activities, the war towards Kokand Khanate. In addition to modern arms, invaders were ruled by special generals who had experience in European wars. Although increase in internal conflicts and struggles for government, the inhabitants of the Khanate got ready to come across with enemies in supporting religion, homeland and pride.

In the 1840s of the 19 th century subjecting the population in the vast Djuz areas of Kazakh, The Russian Imperia enlarged its round of influence.

In 1850 the troops of the Russian Imperia prepared to take a control the Tuychibek fortress by the Ili river of Kukands. The first attack in April 19 th didn't give any benefits, but in 1851 a 500 Kazakh horsemaned group led by Colonel Karabashev came closer to the fortress with 2 cannons. Taking into consideration that the strength of Kukands wasn't equal, they abandoned the fort. The enemy destroyed the fortress. After that they took possession and destroyed fortress of Kokand's Kushkurgan, Kattakurgan, Chimkurgan.

Against the aggression of the Russian Imperia the son of Said butcher Pskandy, the mayor of Okmasjid, gathered 1700 soldiers from Kumushkurgan, Julak, Chimkurgan, Tashkurgan and began to move against them. There were 130 troops from the fortress Xudjaniyaz of the Khanate of Khiva among the army. However, starting for the road with 72 men soldiers and cannon, in 1850 on March colonel Engman from Orol castle started to attack against Kukands in Okchabulak fort in 55km. after the hard war in the morning of March 5, 70 troops were killed, 4 of the aggressions were injured.

In 1852 Rezovskiy, general-colonel of Orenburg, ordered Colonel Blaramburg with 400 soldiers to search the areas of the Syrdarya's banks and find a solution to ruin the fortress Okmasjid. In the same year on July 18, Blaramberg placed near the Okmasjid. The Russian's first attack came to an end with no success. They had to retreat because of not being able to take over the second military wall of the fortress.

While he was withdrawing from there, marching along the river Korauzak and ruining the fortress of Kushkurhan, Chimkurhan and Kumushkurhan, Colonel Blaramberg managed to come back to the Arol fort on August 22. "In this way Russia was able to place with a strong manner on the right banks of the Syrdarya" – X. Ziyayev concluded in his speech.

At the same time the Russian Imperia was struggling against Kazakh Djuzs in their wide areas, occupying Okmasjid was fixed as an important task. For this purpose in 1853 they began to prepare for attacking through land and water ways.

In 1853 on July 3-4 moving to the banks of Syrdarya by breaking diplomatic and international laws on purpose, one of the Russian generals Perzovskiy held Okmasjid with strength for a few months. After some strained attacks for a few days, he occupied the fort. The enemy consisted of 2840 soldiers and navy troops (captain-lieutenant Butakov and lieutenant Erdeli) including a 400 manned group. Among them there were 2500 horses, 1350 camels and 500 Kazakh clerks.

Despite a hard resistance Kukands were lost. R.H.Nabiyev, X.H.Bobobekov and especially Ziyayev reported about it in their monography.

There are some information about the Russian attacks to Okmasjid in native sources. Mukhammad Solikhkhuja in his novel "Tarikhi jadidayn toshkant" linked the Russian assaults to this castle with stealing the properties of barlos and aygir tribes in near places that was carried out by Pskandy, the son of Yakubbek Said butcher, who was appointed as a governor of Okmasjid by Normukhammad.

However, in the Soviet times, it was forbidden to say obviously that patriot people in Kokand were killed in a cruel way when army of the Russian Imperia were invading Okmasjid. But, there are lots of archive documents about this and one of the local history writers, Avaz Muhammad Attor, gave much information of General-Major of Padurov, on July 29 in 1853 in the war of Okmasjid, out of 300 Kokand people 212 (206 men, 4 women and 2 children) were died and 52 (35 men, 7 women and 10 children) were injured.

From the Russian army, 37 died and 77 were injured (17 were fatal condition and 32 were cured).

As Iskandar Batirrishkin states, even during the seize days and explosions that were made during the invasion, Kukand local people did not give up psychologically. According to the informational letter that was sent from Okmasjid to the general of western Sibir on August 3 in 1853, fortress was invaded on July 28. In this letter, it was stated that Kukands were really didn't give up easily.

Invaders took lots of material things including 66 guns, 120 swords, 120 horses, 2 cannons and 1600 bullets of cannons.

In the writings of local history writers, there was started the efforts of Khan Empire to protect Okmajid. Khudoyorkhan, in 1268-1253 sent Shodmonkhujia to the Okmasjid. After coming to the Tashkent, he began his movement with forces of this region. However, since this movement was useless and gave no result, Khan fired Sofibek Davronbek from the position of governor blaming him on do not fulfilling duties. Besides, he killed Shodmonkhujia and Muhammadkarim as a punishment on the view of people in the Urda square.

After troops of Russian Imperia take possession on Okmasjid, they tried to violate Kokand Khanate freely and they adopted their policy to this. When defeated troops of Kokand on Okmasjid wars were punished on square near the palace, the khan and his relatives did not imagine how they came across enemies.

At the end of 1853 Khudoyarkhan sent Kasim commander against enemy to Okmasjid and he joined troops of Kurama, Tashkent and Turkistan to him. Kasim commander collected troops from Fergana and he came Tashkent with 17 cannons, more than 100 wick guns. Here the heads of Kurama and Tashkent consulted with Kasim commander and they were going to delay the war in order to prepare to it. But the Khan ordered them to fight with enemies. On February troops of Kokand fought with troops of Russia with 17 cannons and some modern weapons.

The Kokand Khanate was on bad terms with Russia. The reason of this government of Russia did aggressive policy to the countries of Central Asia.

As a result, there was bad condition on Syrdarya lowlands. In 1853 Russian troops took Okmasjid. In this period the Kokand Khanate fought with Russians for this fortress, afterwards for Turkistan, Almaata, Yangikurgan and other areas.

In 1854 Russian Imperia formed line that was included Perovskiy harbor, 1st harbor, 2nd harbor, 3rd harbor and areas around Syrdarya. This line was border between Russia and Kokand Khanate.

The Russia Imperia postponed taking Turkistan during the Crimea war. Russia was defeated and they lost harbors to the Black sea. Afterward he intended to pass Afghanistan, India and Iran's waterways by Turkistan areas.

Except for this, as they were developing their industry, they needed raw materials bases. These and other factors caused Russia to restart their military actions in Turkmenistan. On the other hand, disagreements, conflicts and wars gave Russia Imperia a good opportunity.

Frankly, Russian Imperia tried to trigger international and tribal wars in Central Asia Khanate in their external politics, even between Russian citizens where lived in Central Asia were split up conflicts. These conclusions are completely confirmed by archive documents. For instance, in letter written by Siberian head, G.Gosford, it is said: —we will use conflicts between Atabans and Saribagishs (at that time tribes were named like this) as a result of mugging and give them the final beat. For this, we should use Suranchi's service who hates the Kokand Khanate and Kirgiz tribes and shoving actions of mugging their cattle. Finally, we should make Suranchi against "Umbet-Ali".

Before Russia Imperia occupied Kokand Khanate, in order to learn its natural resources Russia Imperia drew their scientists. For instance, in collection of documents named "N.A. Severtsov" it is said that N.A. Severtsov, Russian scientist, came to learn Turkistan climate and crossed the border of Kokand Khanate with his 8 rus-kazaki (Russians living in Kazakhstan) scientists without permission. And there were arrested by Kokand Khanate's soldiers. This brought many big diplomatic problems between Russia and Kokand Khanate borders. Moreover, reliable information related to this topic is gathered in this book. According to the collection of these documents, The Kokands gave information Russians about the capture of N. A. Severtsov.

On May 10, 1858 to prove the words of the commander of the Russian cavalry from fort Perovski 300 soldiers and 2 with the cannon attacked the city of Kokand Khanate's Julak fortress. At the same time, he sent a letter to the prince of Turkestan, announces the release of a Russian scientist Severtsov.

Major-General DANZAS goes back to the fort Perovskiy. A few days after the release of a Russian scientist Russian Empire, the original objective was to conquer the mountain slopes a few entrenched.

As a result, the Russian government has been reluctant to sign the documents about the friendship. In one of the documents of Uzbekistan State Central Archive, the confidential letter written on January 19, 1859, a plan of —conquer and control upper parts of the river Chu|| reviewed in accordance with the decree of the Russian Emperor Nicolay I. Among the participants were the Minister of Military Affairs-Prince Dolgorukov, Count Perovski and General infantry H.Gosphord. They decided to take the land Tukmok,

Pishpak, Avliyoota, Suzok, Turkistan and belong to the Syr Darya. They worried about coming to the throne Mallakhon, who has a great reputation, a skilled politician and generals think the invasion need to be completed since 1860 until 1861. On 24 January 1859, the discussion which belongs to District of Orenburgh and west Siberia, discussed this issue. Nikolay Sukhozanet, prince Alexander Gorchakov, Nikolai Metmen, Alexander Knyajevski, Goustaff Gosphord, Alexander Katenin, Baron Lieven, Egor Kovalevski and Nikolai Ignetev took part in this meeting. The meeting was also attended by the emperor himself and approved the plan Gosphord. Thus, the bottom of the river, which does not require a very high cost and any problems, was determined to be completed until 1860. According to the above decision in August-September 1860 Colonel Simmering occupied Tukmok and Pishpak.

Kokand khanate was occupied by the Russian Empire, many historians studied and learned. However, very little research on international relations at the time of Mallakhon. The government of the Russian Empire with Kokand Khanate to establish diplomatic relations with the forces. For example, the military commander of Russia wrote it on November 12, 1862. If the dangerous situation in the neighboring countries of aggression against us in this passage, we use confusion on Kokand khanate. Due to the Crimean War stopped the military actions began in 1860.

Attacked the Tukmok castle on August 26, 1860, Colonel Simmering captured 2 flags, iron cannon, 11 guns, 50 knives, 37 swords, spears 7, 32 pounds of gunpowder and many things. Captain Honkuli asked help from invaders, who fear punishment for defeat.

September 5, 1860 Pishpak placed and 627 soldiers, many things were prey. Russians used 6 Route 600 Russians, Cossacks, 200 volunteers, 12 cannon 4 rocket device in the battle of Pishpak and Tukmok. On 1861, Yangikurgon was occupied. In May 1862 the Russian generals conquer Oqsuv, Pishtepa va Choldevor fortress, in May 1863 an army sent to Turkestan town, on 8 june conquer Cho'loq fortress. On 12 june 1864 Colonel Veryovkiin occupied Turkestan town.

On May 1, 1864, Colonel Chernyayev stormed fortress Avliyoota and captured it. Chernyayev was awarded the rank of general and order for conquered fortress Avliyoota. Thus, the 1847-1864 years, the Russian government has won a lot of land of Kokand khanate. Turkestan and Shymkent cities of Kokand khanate of the most important base stations, therefore the enemy attacked these cities fastly and strongly. Commander came Alimqul to protect the city and the city to organize the defense of the title. July 12, 1864, enemies captured Turkestan. Veryovkin sent unique historic things of mausoleums Khoja Akhmad Yassavi to Russia. General Chernyayev under siege Shymkent, a failed military coup Alimqul.

Finally, in Shymkent, in September 1864, fierce fighting began. Military technical advantage enemy occupied the city on September 22. On April 28, 1865 Chernyayev orders to occupy the castle of Niyozbek. It should also be noted that the organization of the defense in general Alimqul service was great. On May 15-16, 1865 he came to Tashkent

with army of mercenaries in Andijan, Uratapa, Hujand, Namangan and Margelan. Alimqul died on May 21 and began confusion in people. On July 7, 1865, began the negotiations to avoid bloodshed. Chernyayev helds negotiations with the prestigious people of the city, such as Hakimhuja qozikalon, Abdurakhmon eshon, Solikhbek Ohun domla. They were unable to agree and punished, then submitted a false document to fill to Abdusattor Qoraboshi. Then, all of prestigious people forced to sign compulsory, sealed. Treaty copied and it sent to Istanbul through Ignateev, glued to the streets of the city. In a word, after Tashkent occupied, this city revolved to resolve all of political issues which belongs to Turkestan of Russian Empire.

During the period, Russian Empire intensified occupation of Turkestan. Russian used internal wars and conflicts in Jizzakh, in February 1866 came to Uchtyepa. Jizzakh governor Yoqubbek didn't fight, sending a number of food and feed, establish a friendly relationship with them. 300 Russian soldiers returned through to the harsh conditions of the desert to Tuytepa. Emir of Bukhara went to Fergana in March 1866. People of Fergana waited help from Emir. By combining forces, hoped to send out from Turan of the Russians.

Historian Avaz Mukhammad Attor wrote: the trouble occurred in Kokand. 27 years, every year, every month and every day the conflict and strife happening. Among people had no any brave, who protected from enemies.

The war continued with Russians for 10 years. Kokands attacked many times to Oloy, Oqmasjid, Avliyoota, Merka, Pishpak, Almaota, Julak and Kurgan. Many people died in war.

Everyone was aware of this starvation and expensiveness lasted long during the period we are talking about. People went through such an extremely tough situation that even Kokand region and its population faced to tortures of that dark time. Concentrating their last efforts people tried to get back on their feed supporting Khudayarkhan and Amir as ruler. In addition to the harm brought by the war against the Russians, the Amir used to enjoin poor locals to fight against them causing to dreadful damaged here and there by himself. The details of his vicious actions are that the Amir used to send the soldiers of Kokand to the war against Russians earlier being himself two or three destinations behind them. He was not concerned about death of Konkani people trying to remain alive. In April 1866 Khudayarkhan decided not to obey to the orders by the Amir anymore and went back to Kokand leaving the war against Russians.

Beginning from 1867 Kokand-Russia matters began to be dealt with in Tashkent. The right to sign the agreements between the Khanates of Central Asia was granted to the general governor of Turkistan, Fon Kaufman.

Therefore Khanates agreed to make a contract with Turkistan general governance rather than they did with Russian Imperia. Looking at this situation from the point of diplomacy and spirituality, it cannot be considered nothing much but abusing the rights of the independent countries. When it comes to discuss Kokand-Russian diplomacy, one should bear in mind that governors who stayed in the boundaries followed neither instructions of the chief officers in St. Petersburg nor the principles of diplomacy by acting

at their will. Conquest of Tashkent and destruction of Russian formal diplomacy can be an obvious example of this.

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